

A STUDY OF ASTIGMATISM CORRECTION BY VARIOUS METHODS IN PHACOEMULSIFICATION SURGERY

Dr. Jaishree Dwivedi*, Dr. Alka Gupta, Dr. Lokesh Kumar Singh, Dr. N. Gupta

India.

*Corresponding Author: Dr. Jaishree Dwivedi

India.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18103819>

How to cite this Article: Dr. Jaishree Dwivedi*, Dr. Alka Gupta, Dr. Lokesh Kumar Singh, Dr. N. Gupta. (2026). A Study Of Astigmatism Correction By Various Methods In Phacoemulsification Surgery. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Life Science, 12(1), 41–46.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

Article Received on 27/11/2025

Article Revised on 17/12/2025

Article Published on 01/01/2026

ABSTRACT

Cataract surgery has evolved into a precise refractive procedure with the goal of achieving optimal postoperative visual outcomes. Residual astigmatism significantly affects uncorrected visual acuity (UCVA), making its correction during phacoemulsification an important determinant of patient satisfaction. **Aim:** To evaluate and compare the efficacy of various methods of astigmatism correction—clear corneal incision, limbal relaxing incision (LRI), and toric intraocular lens (IOL)—performed during phacoemulsification surgery. **Materials and Methods:** A prospective, non-randomized, comparative study was conducted on 60 patients with age-related cataract and pre-existing corneal astigmatism (<4D) at the Department of Ophthalmology, LLRM Medical College, Meerut. Patients were divided into three groups:

- Group 1: <1D astigmatism – clear corneal incision on the steep axis
- Group 2: 1–2D astigmatism – limbal relaxing incision using Nichamin nomogram
- Group 3: 2–4D astigmatism – toric IOL implantation.

Postoperative follow-up was done on day 1, week 1, week 4, and week 12. UCVA, keratometric readings, and surgically induced astigmatism were evaluated and analyzed statistically. **Results:** All three methods showed a statistically significant improvement in UCVA and reduction of astigmatism ($p < 0.05$) at each postoperative interval. By week 12, 55% of Group 1, 70% of Group 2, and 75% of Group 3 achieved UCVA of 6/6. Mean residual astigmatism at week 12 was 0.05D, 0.03D, and 0.01D respectively, indicating excellent visual outcomes across all groups. **Conclusion:** All three modalities—clear corneal incision, LRI, and toric IOL—are safe, effective, and predictable for correcting astigmatism during phacoemulsification. Clear corneal incision is suitable for low astigmatism, LRI for moderate astigmatism, and toric IOL for higher degrees. LRI provides a cost-effective alternative to toric IOLs, while toric lenses offer superior precision and stability for significant astigmatic correction.

KEYWORDS: Astigmatism, Phacoemulsification, Cataract Surgery, Limbal Relaxing Incision, Toric IOL, Refractive Outcomes.

INTRODUCTION

Phacoemulsification results in better post operative visual acuity (VA) than ECCE at all postoperative intervals. Cataract surgery has evolved over the past few years with new surgical techniques, devices and improvement in the design of IOL.

Astigmatism is a visually disabling refractive error affecting the general population. Spectacles or contact

lenses can be used to correct astigmatism.

Correction of pre-existing astigmatism simultaneously with cataract surgery is attempted now a days.

Definition of astigmatic

In ophthalmology, astigmatism means variation of the dioptric power of the eye from one meridian to another. It can cause blur and decreased visual acuity.

Epidemiology of astigmatism

Refractive astigmatism is common, accounting for as much as 13% of all refractive errors.^[1] The prevalence of astigmatism varies with age, with a high prevalence (approximately 20%) in the first months of life when the curvature of the cornea is very steep.

As infants grow older, the cornea flattens, and the prevalence of high degrees of astigmatism (greater than 1 diopter, D) decreases.

Approach to the surgical correction of astigmatism at the time of cataract surgery.

One way to plan surgical correction of astigmatism is to initially assess the refraction and the keratometry simultaneously.^[2] If good correlation exists as to the amount of cylinder and axis, the surgical planning for astigmatism correction during cataract surgery is fairly straightforward. If, however, there is poor correlation (even though keratometry should be more reliable), surgical correction can be less predictable, even with corneal topography. This is where the "art" of astigmatism correction applies. The surgeon needs to also judge the relative reliability of the astigmatic information. If, after careful consideration, there is doubt as to a reasonable surgical plan, the astigmatism correction should be postponed until after cataract surgery and an adequate time for incision healing rather than astigmatism "correction" or "treatment" is an important subtlety.^[3]

Stepladder Approach to Management of Astigmatism at Time of Cataract Surgery.

Corneal Astigmatism	Treatment Approach
<1D	Incision on steep axis
1 D to 1.5 D	LRI incisions
1.5 D to 2.5 D or more	Toric intraocular lens

Limbal relaxing incision

Limbal relaxing incisions (LRIs) can flatten astigmatism as an adjunct to cataract surgery. LRIs have been demonstrated to predictably alter the corneal curvature by flattening the cornea in the meridian in which they are placed and allowing for a commensurate amount of steepening 90 degrees away. These incisions are made parallel to the limbus. Correction depends upon the length of the incision.^[4]

Limbal relaxing incision can correct 4.0D of astigmatism. Limbal relaxing incisions have several strong points: the procedure is fast and easy to perform; the results are highly predictable and reproducible; and the technology is inexpensive. Incisions can be placed with a diamond knife, multi-use and single-use steel blades, and more recently with the femtosecond laser. LRIs are a great option in patients with pre-existing astigmatism who desire presbyopia correction with a multifocal or accommodating IOL as toric versions of these lenses are not FDA-approved at present.

Location of incision

The closer the visual axis, the greater the effect. LRIs have definite advantages compared with CRIs. LRIs produce smoother, more homogeneous corneal topographies with less corneal distortion or irregularity and are quite effective in low and moderate astigmats (<3 D). They are easier to perform and more comfortable for the patient. Extending the length of LRIs to 10 mm can produce significant added effect for cases with astigmatism greater than 4 D.^[5]

Patients with low (<1.5 D) against-the-rule astigmatism (180 degrees) receive 1, possibly 2 LRIs in the steep meridian. If astigmatism is greater than 1.50 D, a pair of LRIs must be used.

Toric intraocular lens

The first toric intraocular lens model was approved by the FDA in 1998. Widespread use of toric IOLs would not come until later, however, with approval of a foldable toric IOL in September 2005. Toric IOLs have the advantage of being able to correct large amounts of astigmatism.^[6]

Initial toric intraocular lens designs

The axis of the toric correction was along the long axis of the IOL. Linear alignment impressions at the periphery of the optic were placed for use during surgery to aid in alignment and to denote which side of the optic surface had the toric correction. The alignment marks were also used to determine the IOL axis postoperatively.

Advantages

The AcrySof Toric IOL has 3 major advantages over previously used toric lens designs. First, the stability of the lens in the capsular bag has been shown to be excellent, both immediately after surgery and through the first several years after implantation. Second, the foldability and insertional similarity to the commonly used Alcon SA60 lens design make it very easy for the average cataract surgeon to adapt to using this particular IOL model. And finally, the lens design also appears to slow if not prevent the development of the dense posterior capsule opacification (PCO) seen commonly after the traditional STAAR toric lens implantation.^[7]

Irregular astigmatism is not corrected with a toric lens and the toric IOL can make placement of a contact lens to treat the irregular astigmatism difficult.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

- To assess astigmatism prior to cataract surgery.
- To study to results of different modalities used during phacoemulsification for astigmatism treatment.
- To assess final visual outcome.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This prospective, parallel, cohort, non-randomized study

was performed at the Upgraded Department of Ophthalmology, LLRM Medical College, Meerut.

Total 60 patients were selected from OPD and undergone a complete ophthalmic examination that included uncorrected visual acuity (UCVA), refraction under cycloplegia, slit lamp biomicroscopy, tonometry, indirect ophthalmoscopy, automated keratometry and Ultrasonic biometry was used to calculate IOL power using the SRK-T formula in all study groups.

Inclusion Criteria

All patients with age related cataract with preexisting astigmatism of less than 4 D were included in the study.

Three groups were formed on the basis of astigmatic error

Group 1 -Patients were selected with astigmatism of < 1.00D
Group 2- Patients were selected with astigmatism of 1.00- 2.00D

Group 3- Patients were selected with astigmatism of 2-4D.

Surgical management in three groups

GROUP 1- Patients were underwent clear corneal incision at steep axis during phacoemulsification,

GROUP 2- Patients were underwent for limbal relaxing incision using Nichamin nomogram during phacoemulsification.

Group 3- Patients were underwent for implantation of ToricIOL by phacoemulsification.Toric IOL axis and

power were calculated by online acrysof

Toric IOL Calculator

The Alpins Goggins method was used to measure surgically induced astigmatism (SIA).

Post operative evaluation

For postoperative evaluation the follow –up

Day 1

1st week

4th week

12th week

At each visit patients were evaluated for- UCVA on snellen's chart

Autorefracion

Slit lamp examination for-

Condition of wound.

Corneal status

Anterior segment status

Indirect ophthalmoscopy

Post operative complications were recorded.

IOL Power Calculation ultrasonic biometry using SRK/T formula.

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

In the study total number of patients were 60, three groups were made 20 patients in each group, divided on the basis, of pre-existing corneal astigmatism.

Age distribution

AGE GROUP (Years)	Group 1		Group 2		Group 3	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
41-50	2	10	3	15	4	20
51-60	8	40	8	40	8	40
61-70	8	40	4	20	5	25
71-80	2	10	3	15	2	10
81-90	0		1	5	1	5
Age (Mean±SD)	59.45 ±7.42		61.35 ±10.27		59.25 ±9.35	

Patients in group 1 were having mean age of 59.45, in group 2 mean age was 61.35, and in group 3 mean age

Preoperative uncorrected visual acuity

UCVA	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3
Snellen 'visual acuity chart	6/60-6/12	4mfc-6/12	4mfc-6/24
LogMAR (Range)	0.3-1	0.3-1.4	0.5-1.4
Mean ± SD	0.61 ±0.30	0.77 ±0.36	1.015 ±0.25

Preoperative mean visual acuity (at logMAR scale) in group 1 was 0.61, with standard deviation of 0.30.

Mean visual acuity (logMAR) in group 2 was 0.77, with

standard deviation of 0.36,

Mean visual acuity (logMAR) in group 3 was 1.015 with standard deviation of 0.25.

Preoperative astigmatism in three groups

PREOPERATIVE	GROUP 1	GROUP 2	GROUP 3
ASTIGMATISM	0.68D-1D	1.1D-1.88D	2D-3.57D

The range of preoperative astigmatism in group 1 was 2D -3.87 D. was 2D -3.87 D.
0.65D-ID, in group 2 was 1.1 D-1 .88 D, and in group 3

Postoperative UCVA at day 1

UCVA(mean \pm SD) LogMAR scale	GROUP 1	GROUP 2	GROUP 3
PREOPERATIVE	0.615 \pm 0.3	0.77 \pm 0.36	1.05 \pm 0.25
At day 1	0.12 \pm 0.1	0.19 \pm 0.21	0.29 \pm 0.23
P value	0.006	0.007	0.009

The average difference in UCVA (log MAR) AT day 1, significant, taking p value <0.05 as statistically
postoperatively from preoperatively were all statistically significant.

Postoperative UCVA at week 1

UCVA (Mean \pm SD) LogMAR	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3
PREOPERATIVE	0.62 \pm 0.30	0.77 \pm 0.36	1.05 \pm 0.25
WEEK 1	0.075 \pm 0.07	0.12 \pm 0.21	0.05 \pm 0.21
P value	0.005	0.004	0.001

The average difference in UCVA (log MAR) AT Week 1, statistically significant, taking p value <0.05 as
1, postoperatively from preoperatively were all statistically significant.

Postoperative UCVA at week 4

UCVA(log MAR units) mean \pm SD	GROUP1	GROUP 2	GROUP 3
PREOP	0.62 \pm 0.30	0.77 \pm 0.36	1.05 \pm 0.25
WEEK 4	0.055 \pm 0.06	0.07 \pm 0.14	0.05 \pm 0.08
P value	0.004	0.004	0.001

The average difference in UCVA (log MAR) AT Week 4, statistically significant, taking p value <0.05 as
4, postoperatively from preoperatively were all statistically significant.

Postoperative UCVA at week 12

UCVA (logMAR) mean \pm SD	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3
PREOP	0.62 \pm 0.30	0.77 \pm 0.36	1.05 \pm 0.25
WEEK 12	0.05 \pm 0.03	0.04 \pm 0.02	0.02 \pm 0.02
P value	0.003	0.003	0.001

AT week 12 postoperatively from preoperatively were all statistically significant.
statistically significant, taking p value <0.05 as

Ucva at week 12 at snellen's chart

UCVA (atsnellen's chart)	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3
6/6	11(55%)	14(70%)	15(75%)
6/9	8(40%)	5(25%)	4((20%)
6/12	1(5%)	1(5%)	1(5%)

55% patients of group 1 were improved to UCV A 6/6 vision. 70% of patients of group 2 were improved to UCVA 6/6
vision 75% of patients of group 3 improved to UCVA 6/6 vision.

Postoperative Astigmatism at day 1

ASTIGMATISM (mean \pm SD)	GROUP 1	GROUP 2	GROUP 3
PREOPERATIVE	0.65 \pm 0.19	1.5 \pm 0.30	2.6 \pm 0.57
AT DAY 1	0.1 3 \pm 0.22	0.45 \pm 0.24	0.48 \pm 0.47
P value	0.0052	0.007	0.007

The difference in Astigmatism at day 1 postoperatively were all statistically significant, taking p value <0.05, as statistically significant.

Postoperative Astigmatism At Week 1

ASTIGMATISM (MEAN ±SD)	GROUP 1	GROUP 2	GROUP 3
PREOPERATIVE	0.65 ±0.19	1.5 ±0.30	2.6 ±0.57
WEEK1	0.08 ±0.17	0.13 ±0.15	0.11 ±0.44
P VALUE	0.0031	0.0032	0.0040

p value in all the three groups were significant.

Postoperative Astigmatism at week 4

ASTIGMATISM (MEAN ±SD)	GROUP 1	GROUP 2	GROUP 3
PREOPERATIVE	0.65 ±0.19	1.5 ±0.30	2.6 ±0.57
WEEK 4	0.05 ±0.13	0.08 ±0.15	0.03 ±0.12
P value	0.002	0.001	0.0021

P value in all the three groups were significant.

Comparison between three groups for improvement in UCVA at week 12

UCVA(MEAN±SD)at logMAR	GROUP 1	GROUP 2	GROUP 3
AT WEEK 12	0.050±0.03	00.04±0.02	0.03±0.02

THE UCVA(logMAR) in postoperative group was analysed after applying KRUSKALL WALLIS NON

PARAMETRIC TEST and taking p value <0.05 as statistically significant. H statistic is 7.719.

Comparison between three groups for the improvement in astigmatism between three groups at week

Astigmatism (mean ±SD)	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3
at week 12	0.05 ±0.13	0.03 ±0.15	0.01 ±0.12

Taking p value <0.05 as statistically significant.

The p value is 0.012 and this was considered to be statistically significant.

CONCLUSION

Over the past few years, cataract surgery has become quite akin to refractive surgery allowing greater control over the patients refractive outcome. Now patients expect perfect vision after cataract surgery and surgeons strive hard to deliver the same. In this respect residual astigmatism after cataract surgery is viewed as an undesirable outcome both by the patients and the surgeons.

Refractive astigmatism is common. Accounting for as much as 13% of all refractive error. In a general cataract population approximately 10% of patients have astigmatism with greater than 2 D cylinder, 20% have between ID -2 D of cylinder and 70% less than ID of cylinder.

Various approaches have been developed for treating preexisting astigmatism during cataract surgery such as opposite axis clear corneal incision, limbal relaxing incision, toric IOL, eximer laser.

Diagnosing, measuring, and correcting astigmatism create significant challenges for cataract and refractive surgeons.

All the three methods used in our study are effective, safe and predictable method.

However drawbacks of clear corneal incision is that it can't correct high astigmatism, while limbal relaxing incision and toric IOL implantation can correct moderate to high astigmatism.

Limbal relaxing incision is cost effective alternative to toric IOL and can be used in conjunction with cataract surgery to reduce moderate astigmatism.

Implantation of acrylics of toric IOL is a predictive and safe method to correct high astigmatism, the stability of the lens in the capsular bag has been excellent. These lenses also appear to slow if not prevent the development of dense posterior subcapsular opacification.

Outcome after toric IOL implantation are influenced by numerous factors, right from the preoperative case selection and investigations to accurate intraoperative alignment and post operative care.

With the limitation of our study we can't conclude that which study is better or which is best, all the three methods to correct astigmatism during phacoemulsification give good results.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Alio JJ, Agdeppa MC, Pongo VC, El Kady B. Microincision cataract surgery with toric intraocular lens implantation for correcting moderate and high

- astigmatism: pilot study. *J Cataract Refract surg*, 2010; 36(1): 44-52.
2. Muftuoglu O, Dao L, Cavanagh HD, McCulley JP, Bowman RW. Limbal relaxing incisions at the time of apodized diffractive multifocal intraocular lens implantation to reduce astigmatism with or without subsequent laser in situ keratomileusis. *J Cataract Refract Surg*, 2010; 36(3): 456-64.
 3. Carvalho MJ, Suzuki SH, Freitas LL, Branco BC, Schor P, Lima AL. Limbal relaxing incisions to correct corneal astigmatism during phacoemulsification. *J Refract Surg*. 2007; 23(5): 499-504. Comment in: *J Refract Surg*, 2008; 24(6): 562-3.
 4. Kamiya K, Shimizu K, Ohmoto F, Amano R, Evaluation of corneal biomechanical parameters after simultaneous phacoemulsification with intraocular lens implantation and limbal relaxing incisions. *J Cataract Refract Surg*, 2011; 37(2): 265-70.
 5. Mendicute J, Irigoyen C, Aramberri J, Ondarra A, Montes-Mico R. Foldable toric intraocular lens for astigmatism correction in cataract patients. *J Cataract Refract Surg*, 2008; 34(4): 601-7.
 6. Alpíns N. A new method of analyzing vectors for changes in astigmatism. *J Cataract Refract Surg*, 1993; 19(4): 524-33.
 7. Alpíns N, Goggin M, Practical astigmatism analysis for refractive outcomes in cataract and refractive surgery. *Surv Ophthalmol*, 2004; 49(1): 109-22.